

Spectral studies on the interaction of safranin T, phloxin, fluorescein with inorganic ions and their photogalvanic effect

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Manuscript received 6 December 2000, revised 17 August 2001, accepted 28 August 2001

The system consisting of anionic dye fluorescein with inorganic ions in aqueous solution generates photovoltage when studied in photogalvanic cell. Fluorescein dye produces much greater photovoltage compared to other anionic dye phloxin (2,4,5,7-tetrabromo-3',4',5',6'-tetrachlorofluorescein) and cationic dye safranin T (3,6-diamino-2,7-dimethyl-5-phenylphenazinium chloride). The open-circuit photovoltage, the short-circuit current and solar energy efficiency of these systems have been determined. The fluorescence intensity of the dye safranin T and phloxin is quenched in presence of the ions studied while fluorescence intensity of fluorescein is enhanced in the presence of the ions. The absorption spectra of the dye are not perturbed in the presence of the ions indicating no molecular interaction between the dyes in the ground state and the ions. The Stern-Volmer quenching constant and rate constant of growth of photovoltage have been calculated. The experimental evidences support the excited state interaction of the dyes with the ions studied.

The photochemistry of dyes has contributed to the understanding of the mechanism of electron transfer reactions in photoelectrochemical devices¹⁻⁶. Numerous photoinduced redox reactions consisting of dyes and different reducing agents have been studied in electrochemical cells for the conversion of solar energy to electrical energy by chemical means⁵⁻⁹. Phenazine dyes in conjunction with different reducing agents have been found to be efficient photosensitizers for probing charge transfer in photoelectrochemical cells¹⁻⁸. Isabel *et al.*⁹ studied the photoredox reactions of thionine with iron(II), cobalt(II) and manganese(II) by flash photolysis technique for a better understanding of the mechanism of thionine based photogalvanic cell. A detailed literature survey¹⁻¹⁶ reveals that different photosensitizers mainly cationic and neutral dye and reductants have been used in photogalvanic cells but the use of anionic dyes as photosensitizers in the photogalvanic cell for solar energy is rare. Therefore in the present work, the photogalvanic effect of anionic dyes fluorescein (FL) and phloxin and cationic dye safranin T for comparison has been studied in aqueous solution. The photophysical properties of the dyes in presence of different inorganic ions used as reductants in galvanic cells have been studied in aqueous solution.

Results and Discussion

Fluorescence behavior of the dye in presence of inorganic ions : The inorganic ions $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, I^- , Br^- , N_3^- and EDTA quenched the fluorescence of safranin T (ST) and phloxin (PL) in aqueous solution without any fluores-

cence spectral change. The counter ions of the quencher have no effect on the fluorescence quenching of ST and PL. The ions do not quench the fluorescence of FL rather the fluorescence intensity is enhanced in their presence, which has been discussed in the later section. In aqueous medium, the enhancement of the fluorescence intensity with increasing concentration of dyes (in the range 20–40 $\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$) is linear which indicates the absence of concentration quenching of fluorescence of the dye. The Stern-Volmer quenching constants (K_{sv}) were obtained from eqn. (1) for ST and PL and the values are given in Table 1.

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{\text{sv}}[\text{Q}] \quad (1)$$

F_0 and F are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher.

The rate constants for quenching, k_q calculated from the relationship, $K_{\text{sv}} = k_q \tau_0$, are given in Table 1. τ_0 is the fluorescence life-time¹⁶ of the dye molecule. The observed values of $\log k_q$ correlated well with the redox potentials of the quenchers suggesting a charge transfer or electron transfer mechanism for quenching¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The quencher ions had no effect on the absorption spectra of ST and PL in aqueous solution. The reduction potential of ST and PL were obtained by cyclic voltammetry to be -0.467 and -0.171 V calculated with reference to standard hydrogen electrode (SHE). Knowing the excitation energy ΔE_{00} of ST and PL, the reduction potentials of the first excited singlet state of dyes can be calculated. A value of ΔE_{00} of 2.68 eV for ST

Table 1. Stern-Volmer constant (K_{sv}), bimolecular rate constants (k_q) for the quenching of fluorescence of safranin T and phloxin by inorganic ions and binding constants of fluorescein with ions at 298 K

[Safranin T] = 2×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, [Phloxin] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³,
 [Fluorescein] = 1×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, $\tau_{ST}^0 = 1.46$ ns, $\tau_{PL}^0 = 0.05$ ns

Dye	Quencher	K_{sv} dm ³ mol ⁻¹	$K_q \times 10^{-9}$ s ⁻¹	ΔG eV	log K_q
Safranin T	I ⁻	20	13.6	-0.903	10.13
	N ₃ ⁻	16.7	11.4	-0.913	10.05
	Br ⁻	10	6.8	-0.303	9.83
	[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	41	28.1	-1.87	10.45
	EDTA	0.86	0.59	-	8.77
Phloxin	I ⁻	3.67	73.4	-1.10	10.86
	N ₃ ⁻	2.5	50.2	-1.11	10.70
	Br ⁻	0.16	3.2	-0.499	9.51
	[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻	5.33	106.6	-2.07	11.03
	EDTA	2.67	53.4	-	10.72
Fluorescein	I ⁻		K'_c 18.2		
	N ₃ ⁻		28.3		
	Br ⁻		1.0		
	[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁴⁻		42.0		
	EDTA	6.25			

and 2.58 eV for PL and a value of +2.21 V for ST and +2.41 V for PL were realized as the reduction potential of ST and PL in their excited state. The literature value²⁰⁻²² of reduction potentials of the [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻/[Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻, I₂/I⁻, Br₂/Br⁻, N₃/N₃⁻ are +0.36, +1.33, +1.93, +1.32 V, respectively; therefore, the reduction of the dyes in the excited state by the quenchers by an electron transfer mechanism was energetically feasible (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Reduction potential of safranin T and phloxin in the ground state and in electronically excited state and of quenchers with respect to NHE, arranged in an electrochemical series.

The free energy change (ΔG) for the electron transfer step may be evaluated^{18,22} from eqns. (2, 3),

$$\log k_q = \log K_{diff} - \frac{\Delta G}{2.3RT} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } \Delta G = [E_{1/2}^D - E_{1/2}^A] - \Delta E_{00} - \frac{Z_A Z_B e^2}{\epsilon \sigma} \quad (3)$$

$E_{1/2}^D$ and $E_{1/2}^A$ are the polarographic half-wave reduction potential of the donor and acceptor, respectively, ΔE_{00} is the electronic excitation energy of the acceptor computed from the point of symmetry of the absorption and emission spectra of the acceptor, K_{diff} the rate constant for the diffusion interaction between the reacting species, ϵ the dielectric constant of the medium and σ the encounter distance. Plot of $\log k_q$ vs ΔG yielded straight-line for the quenching of the fluorescence of safranin T and phloxin by the quenchers [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻, I⁻, Br⁻, N₃⁻. Slope of the lines 0.4 and 0.36 eV⁻¹ has been obtained for ST and PL, respectively.

The quenchers do not undergo interactions with ST and PL in the ground state. The redox potentials of the quencher couples and dye molecules in the excited state (Fig. 1) and linear relationship (eqn. 4) between $\log k_q$ and ΔG ,

$$\log k_q = m\Delta G + A \quad (4)$$

ensure the thermodynamic feasibility of reduction of the dye in the excited state by these ions by ET mechanism.

Fluorescence behavior of fluorescein : The ions do not quench the fluorescence of fluorescein but enhance the fluorescence intensity, whereas EDTA quenches the fluorescence of fluorescein. With increasing concentration of the ions, the fluorescence intensity increases and then levels to a maximum. Assuming that the dye molecules in the excited state are exclusively in the form of a 1 : 1 type complex with the ions, the ($F_{max} - F_0$) values can be taken as proportional to complex or $[D_{comp}]$ ²³. Thus

$$(F_{max} - F_0) = K [D_{comp}]$$

where, K is the proportionality constant and $[D_{comp}]$ the concentration of the dye in the complexed form. The F value at any state other than F_{max} can be related similarly with the complexed dye $[D'_{comp}]$,

$$(F - F_0) = K [D'_{comp}]$$

Combining the two equations,

$$\frac{[D'_{comp}]}{[D_{comp}]} = \frac{(F - F_0)}{(F_{max} - F_0)} = F_R$$

Therefore, the ratio of the enhanced fluorescence intensity at any stage to its maximum value is a measure of the fraction of dye in the complexed form.

In accordance with the complexation equilibrium,

where D, Q and DQ represent the dye, anions and the complex, respectively. The fluorescence intensity can be used to evaluate K'_c , where K'_c is the complexation constant in the excited state. On the basis of this concept we get

$$\frac{1}{(1 - F_R)} = K'_c \frac{[Q]}{F_R} - K'_c [D_T] \quad (6)$$

The plot of $(1 - F_R)^{-1}$ vs $[Q]/F_R$ should be linear to yield K'_c . The K'_c values obtained from this plot are given in Table 1.

In the presence of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ there is an enhancement in the absorbance with bathochromic spectral shift (Fig. 2). The change from the spectrum of the dye to that of the complex formed by its interaction with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ passes through isosbestic point at 525 nm. It is assumed that the dye interacts with the ion according to the complexation equilibrium (5).

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of fluorescein in presence of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ (a) 0, (b) 1, (c) 2, (d) 3, (e) 4, (f) 5 mmol dm^{-3}

For the determination of K'_c , the complexation constant of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ with *Fl* in ground state, the Scott equation was used,

$$\frac{[D][Q]l}{d - d_0} = \frac{[Q]}{\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0} + \frac{l}{K_c(\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0)} \quad (7)$$

where, [D] and [Q] are the initial molar concentration of dye and ions, respectively, l is the path length of the solu-

tion, d and d_0 are the absorbance of the aqueous dye solution at the absorption maximum of the complex with and without ions, respectively, ϵ_c and ϵ_0 are the respective molar extinction coefficients of the complex and the dye at the absorption maximum of the complex. The K'_c value is presented in Table 1. From the fluorescence data 1 : 1 complex formation is supported. Except $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ all other ions do not interact with fluorescein in the ground state. $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ also forms complex with *Fl* in the ground state and no complex is formed with Fe^{2+} ions. Fe^{2+} also quench the fluorescence of fluorescein. Why ferrocyanide ion and not ferrous ion forms complex with *Fl* in the ground state is not easy to rationalize. This may be due to high charge density on the ion.

Photogalvanic effect : The photogalvanic effect of fluorescein, phloxin and safranin T was studied in aqueous solution using platinum electrodes for both chambers, illuminated and dark at 25°. On illumination, the anode compartment of the cell consisting of aqueous solution of dye and the ions studied, a photovoltage develops which attains a maximum value within 30 min (Fig. 3). Fluorescein dye produces much greater photovoltage compared to other dyes. When the illumination is stopped the photovoltage decreases gradually and after a while the dark value is reached. The

Fig. 3. Growth and decay of photovoltage as induced by illumination of the anode compartment with fluorescein - Br^- aqueous solution and I_2 / I^- redox couple in the cathode compartment

reversible light induced photovoltage generation can be reproduced at least 7–8 times. The open-circuit photovoltage (V_{oc}) has been found to increase with increasing concentration of dye at a fixed concentration of ions (0.1 mol dm^{-3}). The maximum concentration of dye to generate maximum open-circuit photovoltage at a fixed concentration of ions is given in Table 2. But V_{oc} has been found to remain the same with increasing concentration of ions at a fixed concentra-

$$\text{Power of the cell} = \frac{I_{sc}V_{oc}ff}{\text{Area of electrode}}$$

The results indicate that for different dyes the photovoltage generated follows the order : fluorescein > safranin T > phloxin. Among the different redox couples which are easy to prepare, the photovoltage generation becomes maximum with I_2 / I^- redox couple in cathode. Since EDTA is a universal donor and has been used in earlier

Table 2. Characteristics of photogalvanic cells consisting of dye – ion in photoanode and I_2 / I^- redox couple at 298 K

Dye	Ion	Open circuit photovoltage mV	Short circuit current I_{sc} , μA	Solar energy efficiency $\gamma \% \times 10^3$	Rate constants (K). min^{-1}	
					Growth $\times 10^2$	Decay $\times 10^1$
Fluorescein	I^-	1143	4.0	5.6	3.2	6.0
	Br^-	1274	4.0	5.9	4.6	5.3
	N_3^-	1250	4.0	5.8	5.6	1.6
	$[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$	1260	4.0	5.8	3.3	4.2
	EDTA	105	2.5	0.8	2.1	2.7
Safranin T	I^-	503	2.0	3.1	1.2	2.5
	Br^-	394	2.0	2.9	1.9	2.5
	N_3^-	238	1.0	1.8	1.8	1.9
	$[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$	485	2.0	3.1	1.8	2.4
	EDTA	283	1.8	0.9	1.8	2.1
Phloxin	I^-	393	2.0	2.5	0.8	5.6
	Br^-	410	2.0	2.7	1.1	1.6
	N_3^-	401	2.0	2.7	0.9	0.9
	$[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$	356	1.0	2.4	0.9	1.6
	EDTA	94	1.2	0.6	0.9	2.0

tion of dye ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$). The growth of photovoltage of the cell consisting of aqueous solution of dyes in the anode compartment and I_2 / I^- redox couples in the cathode compartment are given in Table 2. From the current voltage curve of these systems, characteristics of photogalvanic cell, i.e. short-circuit current (I_{sc}) and solar energy efficiency (SEE) of these systems have been calculated using the relations (8) and (9) and given in Table 2.

$$\text{Fill factor } (ff) = \frac{V_{pp} \times I_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}} \quad (8)$$

where V_{pp} and I_{pp} are the potential and current at power point which is a point on the current-voltage curve where the product of current and potential was maximum.

$$\text{SEE} = \frac{\text{Power generated in cell} / \text{cm}^2}{\text{Power of incident photon} / \text{cm}^2} \quad (9)$$

where,

works⁶, it has also been used with dye in photoanode compartment like other ions but the photovoltage generation is much less compared to anions. It is interesting to mention that the photovoltage growth and decay of dye-ion system in aqueous solution follow the functional forms (10) and (11),

$$V_t = V_0[1 - \exp(-t/\tau_1) + Z_1] \quad (10)$$

$$V_t = V_0[\exp(-t/\tau_2) + Z_2] \quad (11)$$

where, V_t is the open-circuit photovoltage at time t , V_0 the steady state maximum open-circuit photovoltage, τ_1 and τ_2 are the relaxation times for growth and decay respectively, and Z_1 and Z_2 are constants for the system. From the kinetic studies of the dye – ion system in aqueous solution by the measurements of relaxation times it has been calculated that the rate of the reaction is first and zero order with respect to the concentration of dye and ions respectively. The rate constants of the reactions have been calculated with the help of eqn. (12),

$$k = [\text{Dye}]^{-1} [\text{Q}]^0 \tau^{-1} \quad (12)$$

All the characteristics such as maximum photovoltage, relaxation times and rate constants of dye – ion system are presented in Table 2.

It is interesting to note from the results that the use of fluorescein dye in the photoanode increases the efficiency in photovoltage generation by three times compared to other dyes since quenching of fluorescence by ions does not occur. In presence of EDTA the efficiency of photovoltage generation decreases due to quenching of fluorescence by EDTA. With other dyes the photovoltage generation is much less due to quenching by the ions and EDTA. The rate constant of growth of photovoltage (Table 2) of ST and PL in presence of ions hardly follows a correlation with the rate constant of quenching of fluorescence of the dye ST and PL (Table 1) as discussed earlier.

From the photovoltage generation and spectral results it is evident that *Fl* interacts with the ions forming a molecular complex in the excited state. During the generation of photovoltage the colour of the solution does not change appreciably and photovoltage is generated even if the solution is not deoxygenated by bubbling nitrogen. These observations support the participation of excited singlet dye in photovoltage generation according to the following scheme.

The various steps that take place in the photoredox reaction leading to the generation of photovoltage in the cell consisting of safranin T (cationic dye) and studied ions (Q) in the anode compartment and I_2/I^- in the cathode compartment are

At the anode chamber :

At the cathode chamber :

Here $\text{D}^{+\ast}$ and DH_2^+ represent dye and semidye radical ions, respectively. Phenazyme dye in the excited state is reduced to semi-form by the ions, which is converted to Q by donating a lone-pair of electrons. At the photoanode the reduced dye donates an electron, which moves through the outer circuit and reduces I_2 to I^- or other oxidized forms.

When anionic dyes fluorescein and phloxin are used in photoanode the following reaction may take place :

$\text{D}^{-2\ast}$ is anion radical of dye

Among the dyes, the anionic dye fluorescein produces a large photovoltage in presence of ions, which do not quench its fluorescence. Thus the photogalvanic cell containing dyes and anions absorbs photon energy and this energy is converted into electrical energy by the electrode reaction through the formation of an excited state complex of electron donor acceptor (EDA) type.

Conclusion : Inorganic ions, i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, I^- , Br^- , N_3^- and EDTA quench the fluorescence of safranin T and phloxin where as the fluorescence intensity of fluorescein is enhanced in the presence of the ions. The photogalvanic effect of dye – anion system has been measured using different redox couples. Among the dyes, fluorescein produces much greater photovoltage, which can be reproduced a number of times.

Experimental

Safranin T (ST), fluorescein (FL) and phloxin (PL) (Sigma) were recrystallized from ethanol-water mixture. The salts of the quencher ions were of A.R. (B.D.H.) grade. Double-distilled conductivity water was used for solution preparation. Absorption spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 200 spectrophotometer with a matched pair of silica cuvettes (path length 1 cm) and fluorescence spectra using a Fluorolog F IIIA spectrofluorimeter (Spex, USA) with a slit width of 2.0 nm.

The photogalvanic effect of dyes was studied in a H-shaped cell with all standard joint stoppers. The light source was a projector tungsten lamp (220 V, 300 W) focussed to 30 mW-cm^{-2} . The illuminated and dark chambers were separated by a Pyrex sintered glass membrane, and platinum foil electrodes (1 cm^2 each) were placed in center of each compartment. The illuminated (anode) compartment consisted of dye and aqueous solution of inorganic ions and the dark (cathode) compartment consisted of an aqueous solution of a redox couple. The photovoltage and photocurrent were measured with a Keithley electrometer and HIL 2105 multimeter.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance from D.S.T., Government of West

Bengal and SRF to one of the authors (J.K.G.) is gratefully acknowledged.

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